

NEW PROBLEMS, THREATS AND DANGERS IN THE INFORMATION SOCIETY

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Abstract: this article analyzes the essence and conceptual foundations of the concept of cyber security and the emerging risks and threats associated with digitization in the third millennium.

Key words: information, information inequality, cyber security, security, information security, threat, cyber war.

We will list and briefly describe the new problems, threats and dangers that are waiting for man in the information society and are beginning to face him today.

1. Information inequality. One of the dangers for people in the information society is the problem of information inequality. Factors of social division are accumulation, generation, use of knowledge. Not all members of the information society can make practical use of the new opportunities it can give to people. In addition, this includes not only economic and instrumental-technogenic factors, but also the ability to provide some users with access to society's informatics and information resources, but also humanitarian factors, which mainly depend on the unique qualities of a person. Such factors include: informational, including the linguistic culture of a person, informational competence, education, as well as human motivation, the desire for knowledge and self-study, and the development of intellectual abilities. After all, if a person does not want to be an active member of the information society, then no technology will help him.

The availability of information reduces the motivation to create new knowledge, to develop new ways of knowing. Rejection of knowledge due to its increase in size indicates that internal personal structures are not ready for increased loads. This is manifested in the lack of skills to assess the quality, volume and depth of the received information, which leads to an increase in social inequality[1].

2. Mind manipulation. The second and very serious threat to man in the information society is related to the fact that the development of global networks of television, computer communication, radio communication and other information systems creates many opportunities to influence and manipulate the public mind. By their mental nature, people are very suggestible

and therefore easily subject to targeted psychological influence at the sub conscious level and therefore easily subject to targeted psychological influence at the sub conscious level. This feature is used to control a large number of people, to create illusions, to secretly deprive them of freedom of choice, to change their minds, to motivate people in the right (some group) direction[2]. Manipulation of mass consciousness is the main element of information warfare and is basically the same as introduction to individual consciousness. prepared information. Its effectiveness is reliable and clearly visible. For example, the results of election campaigns for various authorities, as well as the extensive use of very expensive advertising in television programs, are clearly visible. Research results show that television has the strongest psychological impact on a person. The reason is that video information, in addition to affecting the human mind, also directly penetrates into his subjectivity. In addition, the person himself is not worried about it and therefore cannot protect himself from this influence. This is, to a large extent, the basis of the modern methodology of mind manipulation[3].

With a universal means of information dissemination such as the Internet, the technologies of mass mind manipulation are developing rapidly and often have a positive effect, even on people with developed critical thinking, from a completely unexpected side. Ordinary people with an average level of education and cultural development are more and more exposed to this effect, after which an epiphany occurs.

3. Virtualization of society. Another, still little-studied danger for humans in the information society is a psychological phenomenon called virtualization of society. Its essence is that real physical objects, processes and events are replaced by virtual images that are very similar to echoes of objective reality, but are not. These features, as well as the high dynamism of society's information framework, allow creating virtual reality in it. It is perceived by man, along with physical reality. A typical example here can be the so-called derivatives, that is, securities on the stock market, as well as the new virtual currency - bitcoin. Speculative exchange of shares of industrial corporations, appreciation or depreciation of exchange rates in creative financial markets - all these are widely used in the world economy today and, as the analysis shows, they threaten the sustainable development of society[4].

The virtualization of the social space and constant interference in the lives of other people with the help of social networks paradoxically leads to an increase in the feeling of loneliness "in the crowd".

4. Cyber diseases. In the information society, another completely new threat to man is called cyber-disease. These include people's psychological dependence on television, computer games, Internet addiction, and others, which have already become a drug for many in modern society. The maniacal fascination of some young people with computer games promoting cruelty and violence is also frightening. These phenomena are the most common in information-developed countries today, and are one of the negative results of the process of informatization of society. It can be considered that these events will also develop as this process develops. Already, not only addiction is developing, but symptoms of more serious diseases appear, for example, phantom ringing syndrome - it seems to a person that the phone in his bag is ringing or vibrating. Another example of a new disease. Nomophobia - "Nomobilephobia" - fear of being without a mobile phone. Researchers explain the causes of this disease as a result of nervousness when a person is afraid of losing something.

5. Information crime. The formation of the information society opens many opportunities for the development of information crime, which can be directed against the individual, society and the state. This is called computer crime, which is mainly aimed at unauthorized access to the databases of automated information systems of government bodies, financial organizations and industrial enterprises. In these systems, in the process of informing the society, a large amount of confidential information is collected not only about the activities of relevant organizations, but also about personal information about citizens of the country, their addresses, phone numbers, property, income, etc. This information is of course of great interest to criminals. and many of them already use the services of information technology professionals.

6. Information extremism. A sign of informational extremism is physical, material, and moral damage to the legal interests, rights and freedoms of citizens, it is emphasized in the study of R.V. Upornikov [5].

The main characteristic features of informational extremism can be mentioned: the radicality of actions; fight against society; the spirituality and immorality of the content; institutionality; distortion of political and legal thinking.

It is important that the information on the Internet is presented not only in the form of a static "picture", but also that it is characterized by activity, says researcher A.Kh. Valeev[6].

The volume and speed of information flow is attractive to organizers of information extremism. They actually "engage" Internet users in various debates and discussions with the specific goal of changing personal opinions, ideologies, principles, worldviews, and leading to changes in individual or group behavior, as well as creating public opinion that is beneficial to the influential party.

"In the conditions of globalization and the informatization of society, when the obstacles in the control and management of information flows are practically removed, when the national borders of the states are raised to the level, mainly communicatively, the former extremist actions of young people are adopted to influence the minds and behavior of young people," it is said. In the researches of E. O. Kubyakin and A. N. Safronov [7].

One of the important factors of extremist communication in the information field is the phenomenon of spreading rumors. According to E.M. Kulikov, rumors can be divided into two types: spontaneously occurring and creatively created[8]. Spontaneous rumors on important topics are "fruits of folk creativity". Based on political issues, ethnic and religious themes. Creatively created rumors are a clear technology of information warfare (microblogging is now a popular form of "propaganda"). You can agree with the researchers that the social network "Vkontakte" allows you to quickly create a group and quickly spread the information of any content using "reposts" and "likes".

As the researcher V. A. Diehl (V. A. Diehl) noted, the spread of information extremism led to a change in the structure of extremist groups [9]. The "vertical" type of structure (usually headed by one leader) is replaced by the "network" type: there can be several leaders who have separate funds and cover very large territories (be international).

The active development of information extremism is facilitated by the situation when an information event carries a mass information virus[10]. Modern man is faced with a situation where the information about the disgraced actions is more and more focused on the names (nationalities) of the participants, thus the event is interpreted "completely" with a nationalist tone. A "hidden" message, which is more widely spread by social networks, is filled with comments, and is considered by the individual as his own conclusion. We can agree with the researchers that the difficulty (or impossibility) of objective assessment of the received data, personal verification and, as a result, believing it, contribute to the influence of extremist ideas. At the same time, the strengthening factor is the use of ideas that are important to a person: a healthy lifestyle, family, faith, etc. The spectrum of communicative phenomena is very

wide, notes the researcher A.Kh. Valeev, it is the promotion of the values of the consumer society, the promotion of beauty, hedonism and radical political projects.

7. Information terrorism. The concentration of information in automated information banks, which provides remote access to users, is one of the important directions of the process of informatization of society, as it significantly increases the efficiency of information use. However, at the same time, the possibility of unauthorized access to this data, as well as the risks associated with its theft and even intentional corruption, are also increasing. A new phenomenon in the field of information crime is information terrorism. As a result, the operation of the information system can be practically paralyzed. Most often, this situation occurs as a result of specially organized large-scale network attacks. In recent years, these attacks have been repeatedly observed using the opportunities. To solve such problems, a relatively new direction of ensuring the protection of individual information rights is developing. Such rights are already protected by the laws of a number of countries, including Russia, but the perfection and simplification of the protection procedures is still a long way off.

8. The battle for information. Among the threats of the information society, a very special place is occupied by information warfare, the methods and tools of which are already well developed in theoretical and practical aspects. Information wars are already a very common and effective method of conflict in politics, economy and culture. In the future, with the development of the tools and institutions of the information society, it can be assumed that information wars will become more widespread both locally and globally.

In conclusion, in order not to get attached to information, first of all, it is necessary to pay attention to the source of information. It is necessary to make sure of the reliability (scientific, spiritual, cultural), correctness (including historical) of the offered information. For this, acquiring knowledge, teaching to compare the proposed information with previously known information, and to selectively accept information is an important pedagogical problem. From this point of view, the motivational, adaptation to the environment, reflexivity pedagogical-psychological features of protection of students from the threat of harmful information were determined on the basis of systematization of close adults and social factors.

References:

1. Webster F. Theories of the Information Society Translated from English by M.V. Arapov and N.V. Malykhina edited by Doctor of Philology, Professor E.L. Vartanova. Moscow: ASPECT PRESS, 2004. 400 p.
2. Kara-Murza S. Manipulation of Consciousness. – Moscow: 2000. <http://probib.narod.ru/>
3. Melyukhin I.S. Information Society: Origins, Problems, and Development Trends. Moscow: Moscow State University Publishing House, 2002. 208 p.
4. Ivanov D.V. Virtualization of Society. St. Petersburg: "Petersburg Oriental Studies", 2000 [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://m16.medport.ru/USSR/chapters/society.htm> (date of access 30.03.2018)
5. Upornikov R.V. Political and legal technologies for countering information extremism in Russia: author's abstract. dis. candidate of legal sciences. Rostov n / D., 2007. URL: <http://www.dissercat.com/content/politiko-pravovye-tekhnologii-protivodeistviya-informatsionnomu-ekstremizmu-v-rossii> (date of access: 24.03.2018).
6. Valeev A.Kh. Combating extremism on the Internet // Business in law. 2011, No. 6, pp. 125–170. The State Committee for the Study of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation on the Prevention of Crucible Injuries and Crime (Accessed on March 24, 2018)
7. Kubyakin E.O., Safronov A.N. Information Extremism Among Young People as a Destructive Phenomenon of Modern Russian Society // Bulletin of the Krasnodar University of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia. 2013. No. 4 (22). URL: <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=21220235> (Accessed on March 24, 2018).
8. Kulikov E.M. Artificially created rumors: sociological support for monitoring and managing the "information virus" on the Internet // Historical and socio-educational thought. 2011. No. 4. URL: <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=17109285> (date of access: 03/24/2018).
9. Dil V.A. Trends in the development of modern extremism: youth and information extremism // Izvestia TPU. 2009. No. 6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tendentsii-razvitiya-sovremennogo-ekstremizma-molodezhnyy-i-informatsionnyy-ekstremizm> (date of access: 03/24/2018).
10. Glukharev D.S. Counteracting extremism in the modern media space // Bulletin of SUSU. Series: Social and Humanitarian Sciences. 2012. No. 10 (269). URL: <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=17715769> (date of access: 24.03.2018).

